

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**THE CAPACITY OF CALCIUM IN PREMENSTRUAL
DISORDERS**¹Dr Hafiz Muhammad Shahzad Rafiq, ²Dr Ayesha Rehman,³Dr Muhammad Ahmed Abubakar¹Incharge Medical Officer Basic Health Unit Kotla Pathan Teh. Khan Pur District Rahim Yar Khan²Services Hospital Lahore³Medical Officer, RHC Allahabad Tehsil Liaquatpur District Rahim Yar Khan**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:**

Premenstrual disorder (PMS) is a mental and physical problem that occurs only 8 to 11 days before the female cycle. The normal side effects of PMS are emotional episodes, torment and tenderness in the chest, stomach upset, lack of arousal, severe brain pain, back and body torments, cramps, extended affectivity to torments. The severity of the manifestations varies from one individual to another. Late evidence has recommended that disruptive influences on serum calcium levels may extend the side effects of PMS. Our current research was conducted at Lahore General Hospital, Lahore from March 2018 to February 2019. Calcium supplementation may be a powerful treatment for PMS. This investigation was conducted with the evaluation destinations of the various articles identified with the subject. A search on PubMed and Google of different articles containing keywords was conducted.

Key words: Calcium, Premenstrual Disease.

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Please cite this article in press Hafiz Muhammad Shahzad Rafiq et al, *The Capacity Of Calcium In Premenstrual Disorders.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(04).

INTRODUCTION:

In the past, there has been a reluctance to recognize PMS as a real condition. As surveys indicate, about 90% of women are influenced by a similar problem. [1]. The transient event and repetition of the state of mind and physical manifestations during the luteal period of the menstrual cycle have been perceived for quite some time. This wonder is known as premenstrual disorder [2]. Many women have only mild side effects, but others suffer from serious discomfort, leading to a confusion called PMDD (Premenstrual Dysphoric Issue) [3-4]. The term PMS was first introduced by Dalton in 1956. In 1989, the term late luteal phase dysphoric disorder (PMDD) was coined to provide an orderly arrangement of analytical criteria for premenstrual disorders. (Rankin 1995) This clinical component was later named premenstrual dysphoric disorder [5].

METHODOLOGY:

PMS - A (mal)state of mind characterized by swaying, fractures and screaming. PMS - H (hyperhydration) swelling, weight gain, water retention, delicacy of the chest, blockage PMS - C (cravings) side effects of hypo-glycemia (low blood sugar), fatigue, dizziness, craving for sweets, sip of food, heart palpitations, brain pain, headaches. PMS-D (depression), crying sessions, sleep deprivation, helplessness, discouragement. Skin inflammation and skin problems are also normal. Currently, the audit of the various tests indicating the variations in serum calcium levels during the different periods of the menstrual cycle and the use of calcium supplements to alleviate the side effects of PMS is complete.

Physiological role of calcium:

It is the fundamental mineral that has great natural significance. It has an important role in the development of bones and teeth, the control of heartbeat and circulatory tension, the transmission of nerve motor forces, the constriction and unfolding of muscles, the maintenance of the honesty of layers and the action of proteins, as well as in the arrival of synapses in neurons and the focal sensory system. It should be noted that the estrogen that vacillates during the menstrual cycle also controls digestion and calcium intake.

Calcium metabolism:

Virtually all the calcium in the body (99%) is stored in the bone, with only 1% in extracellular fluid and 0.1% in intracellular fluid. The usual range for serum calcium is 9-11 mg%.

Sources:

Our current research was conducted at Lahore General Hospital, Lahore from March 2018 to

February 2019. Calcium supplementation may be a powerful treatment for PMS. This investigation was conducted with the evaluation destinations of the various articles identified with the subject. A search on PubMed and Google of different articles containing keywords was conducted.

Although milk is the incredible source of calcium, it is also found in large quantities in vegetables, nut seeds, beans and long-life foods, wheat, dark colored sugar, powdered milk, almonds, plain yoghurt, bubble eggs, orange, white rice. The prescribed daily calcium intake for adults is 1000 mg to 1200 mg. Calcium intake depends on vitamin D. Nutrient D3 is transformed into a dynamic structure known as calcitriol. Calcitriol advances the union of calcium-limiting proteins necessary for calcium assimilation. The conversion of nutrient D3 to calcitriol is completed by parathyroid hormone. Thus, a deficiency of the hormone PTH also leads to calcium deficiency. Normally, 99% of the separated calcium is reabsorbed by the tubules, and only 1% of the sieved calcium is excreted in the urine [5].

Serum Calcium during the Menstrual Cycle:

Numerous surveys have shown that calcium levels vary in women during different periods of the menstrual cycle. Thys-Jacobs in 2000 showed that ovarian hormones, mostly estrogens, have an impact on the digestion of calcium, magnesium and vitamin D [6]. It was found that estrogen explicitly directs calcium digestion, intestinal calcium retention, articulation, and the release of parathyroid quality, which disrupts serum calcium levels during the menstrual cycle. During the menstrual cycle, estradiol has two pinnacles, one preceding ovulation and the other during the luteal stage. An increase in estrogen level would result in a decrease in calcium concentration, but to compensate for the decrease in calcium level, parathyroid hormone is checked to prevent hypocalcemia.

The most likely clarification regarding the relationship between ovarian steroid hormones and calciotropic hormones is that estrogen has a specific impact on the activities of calciotropic hormones, explicitly parathyroid hormone. It is accepted that estrogen lowers serum calcium by suppressing bone retention in bone renovation and increasing bone mineralization. Late confirmation suggests that estrogen has calcium-hostile properties that impede calcium flow and decrease the cross-sectional area of calcium in vascular smooth muscle [3]. Therefore, it has been recommended that women who do have low serum calcium levels and those with some indication of PMS be increasingly inclined to further reduce

calcium levels during the luteal period of the monthly cycle. (Thys-Jacobs 1998). Upon closer examination, Thys-Jacobs found that changes in calcium-directing hormones were repeated during the menstrual cycle. The investigation revealed a lack of responsiveness of vitamin D digestion, resulting in a decrease of 1, 26(OH) 2 D during the luteal period of the menstrual cycle, which may be the natural trigger for the traditional symptoms of premenstrual dysphoric disorder. In addition, there are various studies on the relationship between hypocalcemia and PMDD. In a review study that pitted women against controls for asserted vertebral osteoporosis, experts found a higher risk of osteoporosis in women with a history of PMS.

Calcium supplementation & Relieving of PMS Symptoms

Current confirmations suggest that variations in serum calcium level may be responsible for the physiological trait pathos of PMS. According to a huge and well-planned investigation by all sides, distributed in a 1998 issue of the American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology, calcium supplements are a viable basic treatment for a wide range of PMS side effects. In a double-blind, false-treatment-controlled survey of 499 visually impaired women, 1,200 mg of calcium per day because calcium carbonate significantly decreased the manifestations of premenstrual syndrome over a period of three menstrual cycles.

DISCUSSION:

These manifestations included emotional episodes, brain pain, food cravings and bloating. In addition, Thys-Jacobs et al. reported a huge halving of the indications in 33 women with PMS in a randomized double-blind, hybrid course of 1000 mg calcium per day [6]. Two clinical reviews have shown that calcium supplementation reduces side effects such as anxiety, discouragement, tension, social withdrawal, migraine and problems, all of which are part of the indications for PMS. In 1993, Penland and Johnson noted that increasing dietary calcium intake to 1336 mg/day in 10 women also decreased mood, agony and water retention manifestations during the menstrual cycle. Penland's investigation further suggests that adequate calcium intake may also help control the side effects of menstrual agony [7]. In addition, the survey led by Shailesh et al found that calcium supplementation successfully alleviates the luteal stage manifestations of premenstrual syndrome. Calcium treatment resulted in a reduction of about half of all average side effects, with a decisive advantage over manifestations such as sadness, mood swings, headaches, touch and chest

engorgement. Calcium supplementation may act by filling a basic physiological deficit, suppressing the release of parathyroid hormones, and decreasing neuromuscular sensation and vascular responsiveness [8].

Based on some non-randomized preliminaries by Elizabeth et al have seen calcium supplements as successful in the treatment of PMS, suggest that high intake of calcium and vitamin D may decrease the danger of PMS. In their research, Cleveland et al (1999) show that among women who bleed, average calcium intake increased from 6114 to 815 mg, suggesting that the vast majority of women at risk for PMS do not take the prescribed intake levels, so it is prudent and safe to include 1.0-1.2 mg of additional calcium each day in their diet [9]. Puja Dullo found in her investigation that serum calcium levels decrease by 7.86% during the luteal stage, while serum magnesium levels increase by 19.45% during the luteal stage. He recommended that the proportion of Ca⁺⁺/Mg⁺⁺ expansion may be responsible for the grunts associated with premenstrual syndrome. Mauskop An, et al have seen that the increase in Ca⁺⁺/Mg⁺⁺ proportions is also linked to the onset of headaches and tension brain pain [10].

CONCLUSION:

Despite its strong predominance, there is an ongoing discussion about its pathos-physiology and corrective supplementation. There are virtually no restorative modalities, for example, calcium supplementation has been shown to be effective in the treatment of PMS. Subsequently, a restorative procedure, such as calcium supplementation during the premenstrual phase, can be used for a powerful and long-lasting treatment. Some research based on the information collected has concluded that there is no relationship between the circumstances and logical outcomes between dietary calcium intake and the reduction in severity of the manifestations identified as premenstrual disorders. Composite research including a physiologist, a nutritionist, a gynecologist can have a huge effect on the strength of women with premenstrual disorders in the decades to come. The future will be an observable one for the best possible treatment of these ladies. In addition to interesting standard treatments such as exercise, relaxation systems such as yoga, music, diets, calcium supplements should be part and parcel of the medical prescription. Further investigation is necessary so that this supplementation can be suggested in an authorized manner as an alternative treatment.

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